

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_4_3_4	
Title	<i>SRNA CS application ("Spremljanje in Raziskovanje Narave z Aplikacijo", literally "An Application for Monitoring and Exploring Nature")</i>
Category	<i>Spatial/Environmental</i>
Purpose of the method	<i>The application records wildlife sightings of citizen scientists. It allows researchers to determine presence and distribution of selected species with many important metadata: location, time, Species, No. of individuals, sex, age, reproductive potential and health status. Collected data can then be used in ecological research.</i>
Effort in time	<i>Several months.</i>
Number of objects investigated	<i>n/a</i>
Data format	<i>Numerical, qualitative, geospatial, textual and images</i>
Description	<i>SRNA is a citizen science app for recording sightings of wildlife observed during outdoor activities. It collects data on 31 species of mammals and 8 species of birds. Additionally, to number of individuals, sex and age, SRNA can collect data on reproductive potential and health status. The application also includes a guide for identifying wildlife and a quiz where users can assess their proficiency to distinguish random pictures of similar wildlife species. SRNA was developed by the University of Primorska and the Hunters Association of Slovenia, within the Step Change project. The data collected will help to improve the knowledge and, consequently, the management and conservation of wildlife in Slovenia.</i>
Basic Literature	<i>List key references related to the tool, formatted in APA style. Include relevant articles, books, or reports that explain or document its use. VELKAVRH, Žiga, DUNIŠ, Luka. (2024). Aplikacija SRNA: nekaj spoznanj iz opažanj lovcev. Lovec: glasilo Slovenskega lovskega društva. [Tiskana izd.], letn. 107, št. 6, str. 265-266, ilustr. ISSN 0024-7014. https://clan.lovska-zveza.si/userfiles/Lovec/pdf/Lovec-2024-06.pdf</i>

	<p>Fakulteta za matematiko, naravoslovje in informacijske tehnologije. (2022). SRNA: Nova aplikacija za monitoring prostoživečih živali / SRNA: New app for monitoring wildlife. Retrieved from: https://www.famnit.upr.si/sl/novice_studenti/srna-nova-aplikacij-1</p>
<p>Contact person within the project</p>	<p>Provide the contact information for the person responsible for the tool within the project (name, email, and, if relevant, their role in the project team)</p> <p>Dr. Elena Bužan, elena.buzan@upr.si, project leader Luka Duniš, luka.dunis@upr.si Dr. Žiga Velkavrh, ziga.velkavrh@upr.si Lan Zirkelbach, lan.zirkelbach@upr.si</p>
<p>Linked material</p>	<p>Link any relevant materials such as questionnaires, digital tools, tutorials, or datasets. Use direct links or indicate where these materials can be accessed (e.g., a shared project folder).</p> <p>https://srna.lovska-zveza.si/login</p>